

COMMUNICATION
GUIDELINES

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BRAND POSITIONING

MISSION STATEMENT

We promote inclusive health and wellbeing for people living in four small- and medium-sized cities as innovative solutions for every town across Europe.

INCLUSIVITY

Inclusivity is one of the **core values** of IN-HABIT, and should be a **guiding principle** in both internal and external communication.

SHOW, DON'T TELL

We don't need to mention inclusivity explicitly in our writing to promote it; it should **resonate through the subjects we write about**.

By talking about inclusivity initiatives - whether by IN-HABIT or one of our partners - we communicate how important it is to us.

This means we:

- Take into account the characteristics and the social / cultural features of different cultures.
- Take into account the capacity of accessing the communication of different social groups.
- Translate (subtitles) video communication wherever possible.
- Ensure local channels have a central role in reaching out to groups of categories and collectives at risk of exclusion.

OUR PILLARS

In our communications, we:

Focus on solutions

Stress accessibility

Promote a gender sensitive & inclusive communication

Build bridges in all our communications

Create engaging stories for children and youth

AUDIENCE

WHO WE'RE WRITING FOR:

LOCAL COMMUNITIES

A large part of our audience are people without extensive experience in investment partnerships, like local authorities, entrepreneurs, and associations.

Many of them will be unfamiliar with terms like 'inclusive health and wellbeing', so our writing should educate and explain what they mean.

We should focus on how these initiatives will benefit communities.

Overly formal writing can sound disingenuous. To make our messaging feel authentic, it should be clear, succinct and conversational - like speaking with a friend.

We should tell our audience what they need to know, without including unnecessary or irrelevant details.

WHO WE'RE WRITING FOR:

EU POLICY-MAKERS & COMPREHENSIVE STAKEHOLDERS

Our secondary audience is policy-makers within the European Union, including scientists and researchers, national authorities, policy makers, fellow project partners, and sister projects.

Their understanding and involvement can be essential to our success.

Because they may have varying levels of familiarity with inclusive health and wellbeing and our project's aims, our writing should explain any terms we use clearly.

When writing for this audience, we should focus on the results we have seen or expect to see from IN-HABIT initiatives (for example, community uptake).

PRESS & MEDIA

GUIDELINES

Communication through the press, radio and TV helps us connect with our local communities.

Activities will be led by a central press office coordinated by WP8/BOT that will coordinate the work for four other appointed key contacts and dedicated person supporting BOT during the project lifetime located in the four cities whose contribution will be empowered by the support of local press offices and official channels and spokespeople where available, one month in advance for each launch.

Local contacts are responsible for collecting local press reviews, identifying and reporting on facts relevant to specific projects, and monitoring local events and agendas.

Before contacting the press, make sure you have reviewed and are familiar with the [project kit](#).

GUIDELINES

To make sure news is attractive to the press, communicators in charge will double-check that:

- The organisation that disseminates the news is also a primary or institutional source of the news, ascertainable and accredited.
- The news is true, recent and unpublished.
- The news concerns people in relevant positions.
- The news has an impact on a vast territorial area and on a conspicuous number of individuals.
- The fact has relevance in the present day or as a function of future developments.
- The news has relevance for the target of the newspaper that is asked to disseminate it.
- The content is of quality: the numbers are fundamental.
- The format in which the news is spread is appealing to the audience of the media chosen.
- The tone of voice of the news is suitable for the media audience to which it is addressed for dissemination.

PROJECT KIT

Your project kit contains:

- Summary of each project, values, participants, milestones
- Accurate and updated information on consortium partners
- Profiles of official and local spokespersons
- Database of authorised photos (of people, places, events), of images and of videos and frames free of copyright that can be shared with the press.

SOCIAL MEDIA

USING HASHTAGS

Hashtags are a powerful way for people to find common interests and initiatives on social media.

We can use project-specific hashtags to:

- Increase outreach and join topic-specific conversations
- Capitalise on existing trends (find emerging hashtags to boost the research with the right audiences)
- Group contents to help people find related posts and discussion
- Bring new opinion into a discussion

OUR HASHTAGS

Below you'll find the complete list of IN-HABIT hashtags:

For general use:

- #Cityvolution #HumanSizeCity #INhabiTownns
- #innovatEU #EU4innovation

For local use:

- #EUforCordoba #EUforLucca
- #EUforAgenskalns #EUforNitra
- #CordobaInnovate #LuccaInnovate
- #AgenskalnsInnovate #NitraInnovate

For topics:

- Culture: #CityShareCulture
- Food: #CityGrowsFood
- Nature: #GreenNewCity
- Pets: #CityCareForPets

REFERENCES

Use of common glossary and hashtags through the social profiles: the use of common words is a key practice of IN-HABIT's DECO strategy because it contributes to achieving the goal of creating a shared code with all local and comprehensive stakeholders and beneficiaries of the project since its inception.

A project Glossary and Gender & Diversity Toolkit, also useful for the project in a more holistic sense, will identify keywords that can become relevant for communication on social profiles and that are also significant on the basis of the most recent trending topics on the social networks used, which in the initial phase will be Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter.

TONE OF VOICE

BRAND PERSONALITY

If IN-HABIT was a person, we would be:

Balanced

Curious

Honest

Insider

Open-minded

Engaging

Inclusive

Professional

Explorer

Determined

Aware

BRAND PERSONALITY

The tone of voice in common institutional communications

- ✓ It should be: mid-formal, respectful, empathetic, aware, thoughtful, passionate, enthusiastic, colloquial, advocate (where needed), scientific (in dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: too self-celebratory (admitted to celebrate the good results of IN-HABIT and the sister and clustering projects), ideological

The tone of voice in local communication

- ✓ It should be: enthusiastic, cheerful, colloquial, engaging, direct, reflective, questioning, reassuring, scientific (in dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: disinterested, aggressive, indifferent, detached, dominant, ideological

The tone of voice in comprehensive stakeholder and media relations

- ✓ It should be: attentive, informative, direct, reassuring, open, expert, scientific (only for dissemination)
- ✗ It should never be: too solemn, too informal, insecure, ambiguous, wavering, too direct, a “bigmouth”

BRAND PERSONALITY

The tone of voice in communication with young people and children

- ✓ It should be: colloquial, interested, close, open to listening, reassuring, enthusiastic, energetic
- ✗ It should never be: ideological, confused, abrupt, obnoxious, disappointed, sceptical, offended, impatient, condescending, blunt or rough

The tone of voice in communication with collectives at risk of exclusion / disadvantage

- ✓ It should be: neutral, colloquial, thoughtful, direct, reassuring, open minded, encouraging
- ✗ It should never be: abrupt, aggressive, indifferent, aloof, condescending, dominant, cynical, derogatory, desperate, hostile, impatient, aggressive, bored, sarcastic, melancholic, sceptical, impertinent

WRITING GUIDELINES

- Have a specific audience in mind. Who are they? Why do they care about what we're telling them?
- Although your language should adapt to the audience, the IN-HABIT brand personality should remain the same.
- Our goal is to be understood, so try to adapt language to the level of the audience.
- Try to avoid using industry language in public-facing messages. When you need to use technical language, include a simple explanation.
- Use contractions ('we're', not 'we are') to make language more natural and conversational.
- Use active voice, not passive voice ('we will <ACTION>' not '<ACTION> will be done').

WRITING GUIDELINES

- Use British English (organise instead of organize, favourite instead of favorite).
- Locally, use bilingual communication when needed.
- When speaking as IN-HABIT, use 'we' - we talk about ourselves in the first person.
- If you need to use an acronym, make sure you include its definition first. For example, 'IN-HABIT is an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to foster Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW)...'
- Politically and socially neutral.
- Clear, simple and concise - try to keep sentences under 25 words.
- Once you have finished, read the sentence aloud. Does it sound natural, like speaking to a friend?
- Include a call-to-action! What do you want the audience to do?

REFERENCES

In each of the four pilot cities, the project will mobilise existing undervalued resources to increase health and wellbeing, with a focus on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion (GDE&I). The integrated approach will combine technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social innovations in selected urban public spaces.

Please remember this approach should always be included when communicating IN-HABIT aims, experiences and stories.

Please find here some useful references:

EIGE - Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication:
<https://eige.europa.eu/publications/toolkit-gender-sensitive-communication>

GENDER-NEUTRAL LANGUAGE in the European Parliament:
https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/151780/NL_Guidelines_EN.pdf

Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English:
<https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/guidelines.shtml>

TONE OF VOICE EXAMPLES

DO

DON'T

Dear sir/madam,

IN-HABIT is helping marginalized people in Cordoba. We are promoting IHW through strategic investment with the creation of a green, creative space in the city centre. Find out about this inclusive initiative here.

WHY?

- Talks about IN-HABIT in third person
- Uses US English (marginalized)
- Uses acronym IHW without an explanation
- Doesn't use contraction 'we're'
- Includes unnecessary details
- Language is too formal, not personal

DO

DON'T

Dear sir/madam,

I'm writing to request your assistance for our project in Nitra. We would like you to support our cause to begin construction on an 8 kilometer cycle track.

Our vision is the eventual creation of a bicycle link between the industrial park and Dražovce and the main city, and it will cost between <PRICE> and <PRICE>.

This is far beyond our means, therefore, we are asking for assistance from <ORGANISATION / DONOR>s in the area.

Yours sincerely,
<NAME>

WHY?

- Doesn't focus on what the project will achieve.
- Sir/madam is outdated and overly formal.
- 'I'm writing to...' is unnecessary; the reader already knows you're writing!
- It doesn't explain the background around the project – so why would this person help?
- Language is unnecessarily complex and formal.
- Numbers below 10 should be spelled.
- UK spelling – 'kilometre', not 'kilometer'.
- Does not tell the reader what it would like them to do at the end.

DO

We've been partnering with <PARTNER> in Nitra, Slovakia to create an eight kilometre cycle track linking the industrial park and Dražovce district with the main city. Find out more...

DON'T

Because of congestion, public services provision and inclusion, the promotion of alternative modes of transport like cycling is being invested in by the municipality of Nitra.

WHY?

- Messaging doesn't focus on a solution
- Does not provide the audience with a practical insight into what is happening in the city
- Uses passive tense, not active

DO

Lucca is investing in animal welfare to promote wellbeing for its citizens. Find out how initiatives like the Cohabitation Human-animal Regulation are helping. <https://bit.ly/lucca>

#inclusivehealthandwellbeing #animalwelfare #INhabiTowns

DON'T

Relevant resources have been increasingly invested in by the municipality of Lucca for improving the wellbeing of its inhabitants, and one such initiative is Cohabitation Human-animal Regulation which receives its funding from a range of EU-mandated investment bodies.

WHY?

- Uses passive tense, not active
- 'Relevant resources' is vague and unclear
- It's too long and filled with unnecessary details
- No call-to-action or hashtags

CONTACT

GET IN TOUCH

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